

Studies on Indigoid Dyes. Part III. 2-(5-Iodo)thionaphthene-9'-phenanthrene Indigo

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Six new dyes have been prepared by condensing 5-iodothioindoxyl with phenanthraquinone and its derivatives, aceanthrenequinone, and β -naphthoquinone. The dyeing properties of the compounds have been studied and their absorption maxima recorded.

The present investigation was undertaken with the object of studying the colour and chemical constitution of the thioindigoid dyes.

Six new dyes have been synthesised by condensing 5-iodothioindoxyl with phenanthraquinone, 2-bromo-, 4-nitro-, 2,7-dinitro-phenanthraquinones, β -naphthoquinone, and aceanthrenequinone in glacial acetic acid using hydrochloric acid as a catalyst. The dyes after preparation were boiled with ethanol to remove the unchanged constituents and were then crystallised from suitable solvents. The absorption maxima of the dyes were determined in pyridine solution. The dyeing properties of the compounds have been studied by developing shades on cotton from alkaline hydrosulphite vat.

2-(5-Iodo) thionaphthene-9'-phenanthrene indigo.

The dyes belonging to this group are dark reddish violet in colour, dissolve in high-boiling solvents such as pyridine, aniline, and nitrobenzene and also in concentrated sulphuric acid producing characteristic coloration; the original dyes are reprecipitated by treatment of the acid solution with water.

Dyes derived from 5-iodothioindoxyl and phenanthraquinone are only partly reducible by alkaline hydrosulphite whereas the other compounds, especially the nitro and the dinitro compounds, are easily reducible. The colour of the phenanthrene indigos are not fully developed on cotton, except that of 4'-nitro compound, although these dyes are deeply coloured and it is a drawback of this series of dyes'.

Some of the characteristic properties of the dyes are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I

2-(5-I) T=2-(5-iodo)thionaphthene.		PI=phenanthrene indigo.		
Dye.	Colour in H ₂ SO ₄ .	Shade on cotton.	$\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{pyridine}}$	log ϵ .
2-(5-I) T-9'-PI	Deep green	Reddish violet	564 m μ	3.922
2-(5-I)T-9'- (3'-bromo) -PI	Deep yellowish green	Do	463	4.096
2-(5-I) T-9'- (4'-nitro)-PI	Do	Bluish violet	556	3.858
2-(5-I) T-9'- (2',7'-dinitro)-PI	Green	Brownish chocolate	567	3.799
2-(5-I) T-acenanthrenequinone	Dirty greenish brown	Reddish brown	513	3.944
2-(5-I) T- β -naphthoquinone	Deep green	Reddish violet	518	—

The absorption maxima of phenanthraquinone dyes are of the order: 2', 7'-dinitro > unsubstituted > 4'-nitro > 2'-bromo.

It is evident from above that the weighting of the dye molecule has, contrary to expectations, not resulted in enhanced absorption. The intensities of the dyes fall in the order: 2'-bromo > unsubstituted > 4'-nitro > 2', 7'-dinitro.

The dyes, 2-(5-iodo)thionaphthene-1'-acenanthrenequinone and 2-(5-iodo)thionaphthene-2'- β -naphthylene indigo were synthesised in order to study the influence of complexity of the right half part of the dye molecule. It has been observed that the acenanthrenequinone dye absorbs at a shorter wavelength than the corresponding simple dye acenanthrenequinone (absorption maximum = 527.5 m μ). Thus an increase in complexity by the fusion of benzene ring to acenanthrene part of the molecule has led to a hypsochromic shift. The dye derived from β -naphthoquinone absorbed at a shorter wave length than the acenanthrenequinone dye, as expected.

On comparing the absorption maxima of 5-iodo dyes of the isatin ($\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{pyridine}} = 517.5$ m μ), acenanthrenequinone ($\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{pyridine}} = 527.5$ m μ), and phenanthraquinone ($\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{pyridine}} = 564$ m μ), it is quite evident that by increasing the molecular weight of the diketone part, a marked shift is observed towards the red end of the spectrum.

EXPERIMENTAL

2-(5-Iodo)thionaphthene-9'-phenanthrene Indigo.—A mixture of 5-iodothioindoxyl (0.414 g.) and phenanthraquinone (0.312 g.) were dissolved in boiling glacial acetic acid (40 ml) and was treated with HCl (conc., 2.5 ml). A red crystalline mass separated immedi-

ately. The mixture was boiled for further 30 minutes and treated as usual to remove impurities. The dye (0.45 g., 64.4%) was recrystallised from xylene yielding small star-shaped crystals, m.p. 282-83°. (Found: I, 27.1; S, 6.7. $C_{22}H_{11}O_2IS$ requires I, 27.25; S, 6.86%).

2-(5-Iodo)thionaphthene-9'-(2'-bromo)phenanthrene indigo was prepared in the usual manner by boiling a solution of 5-iodothioindoxyl (0.276 g.) and 2-bromophenanthraquinone (0.287 g.) in glacial acetic acid (30 ml) with HCl (conc., 3 ml) for 15 minutes in an atmosphere of carbon dioxide. The dye precipitated (0.33 g., 66.6%) was recrystallised from pyridine. The dye did not melt till 310°. (Found: Br+I, 38.1. $C_{22}H_{10}O_2$ -BrIS requires Br+I, 37.98%).

2-(5-Iodo)thionaphthene-9'-(4'-nitro)phenanthrene indigo separated as a deep violet crystalline precipitate on treating a boiling solution of 4-nitrophenanthraquinone (0.253 g.) and 5-iodothioindoxyl (0.276 g.) in glacial acetic acid (30 ml) with HCl (conc., 3 ml) and on heating the mixture for 30 minutes. The dye (0.42 g., 82.2%) was recrystallised from benzene in clusters of small needles, m.p. >310°. (Found: I, 25.0. $C_{22}H_{10}O_4$ -NIS requires I, 24.85%).

2-(5-Iodo)thionaphthene-9'-(2',7'-dinitro)phenanthrene indigo was prepared by dissolving 5-iodothioindoxyl (0.276 g.) and 2,7-dinitrophenanthraquinone (0.298 g.) in glacial acetic acid (50 ml) and refluxing the mixture with HCl (conc., 2 ml) in an atmosphere of CO_2 for about 30 minutes. It was recrystallised from nitrobenzene, m.p. >310°. (Found: I, 22.7. $C_{22}H_9O_6N_2$ IS requires I, 22.84%).

2-(5-Iodo)thionaphthene-1'-aceanthrenone.—A hot solution of aceanthrenequinone (0.232 g.) and 5-iodothioindoxyl (0.276 g.) in glacial acetic acid (25 ml) was treated with HCl (conc., 2 ml), when a dark red crystalline material (0.32 g., 65.3%) separated. It was recrystallised from xylene, m. p. 232°. (Found: I, 26.1; S, 6.5. $C_{24}H_{11}O_2IS$ requires I, 25.91; S, 6.53%).

2-(5-Iodo)thionaphthene-2'- β -naphthylene Indigo.— β -Naphthoquinone (0.158 g.) was dissolved in glacial acetic acid (35 ml) and 5-iodothioindoxyl (0.276 g.) was added to it. To the resulting red solution HCl (conc., 5 ml) was added when a cluster of deep red needles separated immediately. The reaction mixture was then boiled for 20 minutes. The dye (0.2 g.) was crystallised from xylene, m.p. 259°. (Found: I, 30.3; S, 7.75. $C_{18}H_9O_2IS$ requires I, 30.5; S, 7.69%).